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Scoping Review of the Effects of Dietary Supplements on Postpartum Depression

Shian Ming Chen¹, Anne TM Konkle^{1,2,3}

¹ Interdisciplinary School of Health Sciences, University of Ottawa, Ottawa, Canada

² School of Psychology, University of Ottawa, Ottawa, Canada

³ University of Ottawa Brain and Mind Research Institute, Ottawa, Canada

Correspondence: Anne TM Konkle, Interdisciplinary School of Health Sciences, University of Ottawa, Ottawa, Ontario, K1N 6N5, Canada. Tel: 1-613-562-5800 ext 3457 -. E-mail: Anne.Konkle@uOttawa.ca

Abstract

Postpartum depression (PPD) can emerge as one of many maternal risks during the postpartum period. Though antidepressants have traditionally treated PPD, dietary supplements have been increasingly studied as a more accessible remedy, focusing on prevention. The goal of this study is to consolidate information about the effects of dietary supplements on PPD. A scoping review was conducted to identify a possible relationship between various supplements and PPD, using relevant studies on PubMed and Medline published between January 1, 2010 and February 1, 2020. Only English language literature with human subjects was included. 39 articles (from 606 articles originally retrieved) were included and summarized under headings related to: vitamins; minerals; fatty acids; antibiotics and probiotics; and, combination of supplements. The results revealed that dietary supplementation with Vitamin D, multivitamins, selenium, n-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA), or probiotics generally lead to decreased PPD risk. Supplementation with calcium, magnesium, zinc, iodine, iron, or any B-vitamins has no effect on PPD, although there are conflicting reports regarding folate, Vitamin D, and n-3 PUFA. Furthermore, antibiotic usage and n-6 PUFA intake have correlated with increased PPD risk. Studies assessing supplement co-exposure were limited. The results of this review are mixed, with some dietary supplements having a positive effect and others having a negative or no association with PPD. This review highlights the limited knowledge regarding the effects of selenium, iodine, probiotics, and antibiotics. Further research is needed to study the combined effects of various supplements on PPD, as mothers often take multiple supplements during pregnancy.

Keywords: Antibiotic, Dietary Supplement, Maternal Mental Health, Mineral, Omega-3 Fatty Acid, Omega-6 Fatty Acid, Postpartum Depression, Probiotic, Vitamin

1. Introduction

1.1 Postpartum Depression

Postpartum depression (PPD) is a common mental disorder that affects mothers with a variety of symptoms. Differing from the 'baby blues' which requires no treatment, PPD is defined in the American Psychiatric Association's *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition* (DSM-V) as a major depressive disorder that has an onset within 1 month of childbirth (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). However, cases of PPD can start during the pregnancy period and/or may have onset beyond the first postpartum

month (Gavin et al., 2005). Symptoms of PPD often include sleep disturbances beyond those associated with baby care, overwhelming anxiety, a loss of energy, feelings of worthlessness or guilt, and in more severe cases, thoughts of suicide and harm to the baby (American Psychiatric Association, 2013).

The prevalence of PPD varies between countries, with higher ranges among lower- and middle- income nations. In 2012, a cross-sectional study found a point prevalence of approximately 7.48% in Canadian women, while other studies have found that the global prevalence of PPD is approximately 17.7%, ranging from 3% in Singapore to 38% in Chile (Dennis, Heaman, & Vigod, 2012; Hahn-Holbrook, Cornwell-Hinrichs, & Anaya, 2018). Nations with higher rates of income inequality, maternal and infant mortality, or women of childbearing age working ≥ 40 hours a week have higher rates of PPD (Hahn-Holbrook et al., 2018). The global prevalence is set to rise over time, with differences in wealth inequality and maternal health factors explaining the majority of prevalence variation among countries.

Many individual risk factors also increase the risk of a mother developing PPD. The strongest risk factor for PPD is a history of mood or anxiety disorders, especially if left untreated during pregnancy (Stewart & Simone, 2016). In these cases, mothers can be 2-3 times more likely to develop PPD (Dennis et al., 2012; D. Nielsen, Videbeck, Hedegaard, Dalby, & Secher, 2000). Likewise, if a mother has a positive family history of PPD, she tends to be more at risk for the disease, with an odds ratio (OR) of approximately 1.6 (D. Nielsen et al., 2000). Furthermore, social risk factors for PPD can include low household income, low partner support, incidences of interpersonal violence, marital conflict, poor self-perceived maternal health, and young maternal age (Dennis et al., 2012; Stewart & Simone, 2016).

Early screening and detection of PPD are widely known to be beneficial for the mother in reducing the severity of her symptoms. However, the best method for detecting postpartum depression remains controversial, and many diagnostic tools are used around the world. Most commonly used is the Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS), where a score ≥ 13 is often used as an indicator of PPD (Boyd, Le, & Somberg, 2005). Its widespread use has led it to be translated into numerous languages and modified according to specific national guidelines (Boyd et al., 2005). Another common self-report instrument is the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI); a score ≥ 30 is usually indicative of PPD (Boyd et al., 2005). Similar to the EPDS, it has been translated and used in many different languages. Many other diagnostic tools are available, including the Bromley Postnatal Depression Scale (BPDS) and the Self-Rating Depression Scale (SDS), but these are less used due to low sensitivity and low positive predictive values (Boyd et al., 2005).

Current treatment for PPD includes psychotherapy and antidepressants, but studies are increasingly reporting that these therapies have milder effects on PPD than initially believed. Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors, such as fluoxetine, sertraline and paroxetine, are the most commonly used antidepressants, but studies are now doubting their efficacy. In a systematic review by Shama & Sommerdyk (2013), antidepressant usage failed to show significant improvements in PPD symptoms compared to a placebo or psychotherapy alone (Sharma & Sommerdyk, 2013). Furthermore, some antidepressants were found to have higher PPD remission rates compared to the placebo-control groups (Sharma & Sommerdyk, 2013). In a meta-analysis by Cuijpers, Brännmark, & van Straten (2008), results showed that psychological treatments, including psychotherapy, have smaller effect sizes on PPD compared to those usually found for treatment on other types of depression (Cuijpers, Brännmark, & Straten, 2008). Similarly, evidence showed that psychological treatment often does not have a significant long-term effect on PPD (i.e. 6-12 months follow-up) (Cuijpers et al., 2008).

Unfortunately, compliance with PPD treatment is not deemed optimal either. Boath, Bradley, & Henshaw's (2004) observational study found that nearly 50% of breastfeeding participants with PPD did not take their prescribed antidepressants for various reasons (Boath, Bradley, & Henshaw, 2004). The most common explanations for a lack of compliance were misunderstandings about medication, including the belief that the antidepressants were addictive and can impact child development, or a lack of perceived benefit (Boath et al., 2004). Other studies have highlighted that obstacles to psychotherapy also limit patient compliance, including stigma, cost, and limited access to psychotherapists (Stewart & Simone, 2016).

The conflicting results regarding the lack of efficacy and compliance to current treatment highlights the need for more effective remedies with which women are likely to comply.

1.2 Dietary Supplements

Since the turn of the century, there has been a sudden growth in interest in the use of dietary supplements to treat various ailments, including depression. According to the 'WHO Traditional Medicine Strategy 2014-2023', over 100 million Europeans regularly use complementary medicine, including dietary supplements; this number increases in Africa, Asia, Australia and North America (World Health Organization [WHO], 2013). Furthermore, one New Zealand study reported that over 63% of participants with current depressive episodes take at least one supplement daily, with an average of 2.8 dietary supplements taken daily (Silvers, Woolley, & Hedderley, 2006). Many people around the world use daily dietary supplements; however, these supplements can also be taken in addition to traditional prescribed pharmaceuticals when used as a potential remedy for an illness like depression. Nevertheless, there is a general dearth of information regarding the combinatory effects of the two when taken together. These findings suggest that dietary supplements are generally considered by the public to be beneficial for health problems, including depression, possibly due to the belief that it is 'more natural.' Despite the public's perception, there are relatively few studies that assess the effects of various supplements on ailments, in particular PPD.

1.3 Current Study

We are interested in the effects of various common dietary supplements, taken by the mother during the prenatal or early postpartum period, on postpartum depression. A clearer view is urgently needed to better understand and clarify the effects of various dietary supplements on PPD. This knowledge can then be applied to help increase adherence to treatment, using scientifically proven effective supplements, although future correlational studies will be needed to verify this potential relationship.

This scoping review aims to assess the positive and negative effects of various common dietary supplements, taken prenatally or postpartum, on maternal PPD. It will explore the possibility of different supplements as risk or protective factors for developing postpartum depression among reproductive age women. More specific research objectives include: (1) to determine whether present literature supports a link between various supplements and postpartum depression; (2) to assess whether specific supplements provide a higher risk for postpartum depression, and thus whether pregnant women should avoid these supplements; and, (3) to assess whether specific supplements help provide protection against postpartum depression, and thus whether pregnant women should use these supplements. As there is currently no study outlining this potential relationship, a scoping review was chosen over a systematic review to provide an overview of the current knowledge and to act as a potential precursor to a more vigorous systematic review.

2. Methods

2.1 Eligibility Criteria

For inclusion as part of this review, the following were fulfilled:

1. Studies: journal articles (peer-reviewed), randomized-controlled trials, prospective studies, retrospective studies, cross-sectional studies, case-control studies, exploratory studies, and analysis of primary data.
2. Participants: women, single or married, first-time pregnancy or otherwise, and vaginal or Caesarean birth.
3. Interventions (dietary supplement exposure): Vitamin B, Vitamin D, multivitamins, omega-3 fatty acids, omega-6 fatty acids, calcium, zinc, magnesium, iodine, selenium, iron, folate, antibiotics, *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* HN001 probiotics, multi-nutrients and a combination of supplements.
4. Outcome: all types of methods for the potential diagnosis of PPD symptoms were considered: Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS), Beck's Depression Inventory (BDI), Centre for Epidemiologic

Studies-Depression (CES-D) scores, the Bromley Postnatal Depression Scale (BPDS) and the Self-Rating Depression Scale (SDS), and self-diagnosed PPD.

Studies were excluded if maternal PPD scores or symptoms were not the primary measured outcome.

2.2 Search Strategy

Comprehensive literature searches were conducted to retrieve articles of interest from 2 databases: Medline and PubMed.

A list of key words was developed to correspond with terms related to the fields of interest —postpartum depression and dietary supplements — based on preliminary research on common supplements mothers take during the pregnancy period. Trial and error was then used to identify the best key words and subject headings for each database. The key words for dietary supplements included both vague and specific terms (e.g. ‘Dietary Supplements’ and ‘Docosahexaenoic Acids’). The complete lists of key words used for the Medline search is found in Table A in the Appendix. The complete lists of key words for PubMed is found in Table B in the Appendix.

2.3 Data Extraction

Covidence (Veritas Health Innovation Ltd, Melbourne, Australia), an online systematic review managing program, was used to import and evaluate the extracted studies from the two databases. Duplicate articles were automatically removed by Covidence, and one reviewer evaluated the removed duplicates to ensure that the proper articles were excluded.

Two review stages were then completed to assess and select the articles used in this review. Firstly, titles and abstracts were evaluated by one reviewer based on the following exclusion criteria: (1) publication date before January 1, 2010; (2) neither titles nor abstracts described any type of dietary supplement nor PPD. Secondly, a full-text review was completed by one reviewer to determine the included articles, based on the eligibility criteria listed below. See Figure 1 for a visual representation of the article screening process.

2.4 Eligibility Criteria

All studies included in this analysis: (1) involved human models; (2) included direct or indirect exposure to vitamins, minerals, fatty acids, antibiotics, or probiotics; (3) had a primary outcome involving PPD symptoms or diagnosis at any timepoint postpartum, using tests such as, but not limited to, the EPDS, BDI, and self-reported diagnosis; and, (4) analyzed quantitative data, whether primary source or secondary source data.

Studies were excluded from this analysis during the full-text screening if: (1) animal or rat models were used; (2) interventions other than exposure to vitamins, minerals, fatty acids, antibiotics, or probiotics were used; (3) maternal PPD scores or symptoms were not the primary measured outcome; (4) the study was grey literature or a literature review (scoping review or systematic review); (5) any remaining duplicate articles remained; (6) the study was written in a language other than English; or, (7) the full text was not available.

Studies were included irrespective of their definition of PPD. Likewise, studies were included regardless of the geographic location or type of PPD test that was used. The ten-year time frame for eligible articles in this review was set to include articles that likely used more modern diagnostic criteria, while also including as much information as possible, due to the novelty of this topic.

2.5 Data Analysis

Given our interest in looking at different types of studies, and the varied outcomes associated with each of these studies, we decided to conduct a narrative synthesis. This approach allowed us to include as many studies as possible, as well as provide a comprehensive analysis of the studied supplements.

3. Results

The initial search strategy yielded 606 articles from the two databases. After automatic de-duplication, 366 articles were admitted to level 1 screening. After both screening phases, 39 articles were included in the review. See Figure 1 for a PRISMA diagram outlining the screening process. Of the 39 included articles, one focused on antibiotics, one focused on probiotics, 15 studied fatty acids, four investigated minerals, and 19 focused on vitamins. Four studies focused on a combination of various minerals and vitamins on PPD. Note that this number exceeds 39 as some articles researched multiple supplements simultaneously.

3.1 Quality Assessment

The quality of the cohort studies (n=25) was assessed using the CASP (Critical Appraisal Skills Programme) checklist. Of the 25 articles, 2 had poor overall quality, 11 had a satisfactory level of overall quality, and 12 had a good of overall quality. Please refer to Table C in the Appendix for the overall quality assessment of each of the cohort studies.

The quality of the case-control studies (n=2) was assessed using the Downs and Black Checklist. Both the Abedi et al. (2018) and N. O. Nielsen et al. (2013) studies were considered to be of satisfactory quality. The Abedi et al. (2018) study had a Downs and Black Checklist score of 22 out of a possible 32 points, while the N. O. Nielsen et al. (2013) study had a score of 25 out of 32. Please see Table D in the Appendix.

The quality of the cross-sectional studies (n= 2) was assessed using the Downs and Black Checklist. Please refer to Table D in the Appendix for the overall quality assessment of each of the cross-sectional studies. Both the Cosatto, Else, & Meyer (2010) and Lin et al. (2019) studies were of satisfactory quality. The Cosatto, Else, & Meyer study (2010) had a Downs and Black Checklist score of 22 out of a possible 32 points, while the Lin et al. (2019) study had a score of 25 out of 32.

The quality of the randomized-controlled trials (n=9) was assessed using the Cochrane Risk of Bias tool. The judgement for each entry was labelled with a risk of bias of 'low risk', 'high risk', or 'unclear risk', with the 'unclear risk' category indicating either a lack of information or uncertainty of the potential for bias. Of the articles, Amini et al. (2020), Fard et al. (2017), Makrides et al. (2010), Nguyen et al. (2017), and Slykerman et al. (2017) were considered to have low risk of bias, with zero or one classification of 'unclear risk' of bias. Williams et al. (2016) had one classification of 'high risk' for potential reporting bias, while Paoletti et al. (2013), Vaz et al. (2017), and Vaziri et al. (2016) likely have high risk of bias in their respective articles. Please refer to Table E in the Appendix for the overall quality assessment of each of the randomized-controlled trials.

3.2 Analysis of Results

3.2.1 Vitamin D

Fourteen studies investigated the effects of Vitamin D on postpartum depression, nine of which focused specifically on 25-hydroxycholecalciferol, or 25(OH)-D, a pre-hormone produced by the hydroxylation of Vitamin D3. Typically, Vitamin D supplementation has been shown to decrease hypertensive disorders and other, especially musculoskeletal, comorbidities of pregnancy (Mithal & Kalra, 2014). The mothers in each of the included studies had no known prior health issues, but it is not known whether they had also ingested other supplements, as the studies did not inquire about other supplementation. Results from these studies were mixed,

with some articles indicating protective effects of Vitamin D, while others concluded that it has no effect on PPD risk (Table 1). Note that serum 25(OH)-D levels were used as an objective measure of maternal vitamin intake.

Using prospective cohort designs, three articles concluded that Vitamin D was ineffective in reducing PPD symptoms, while five articles determined that Vitamin D was protective against the depression. Of the three articles with statistically insignificant results, Gould et al. (2015) compared umbilical cord 25(OH)-D levels with EPDS scores at 6 weeks and 6 months postpartum. At both times, vitamin levels were not significantly different between mothers with PPD and mothers without PPD (Gould et al., 2015). In the Leung et al. (2013) and Miyake et al. (2016) studies, Vitamin D supplementation during gestation was self-reported by mothers to determine possible correlations with EPDS scores ≥ 10 and Centre for Epidemiologic Studies-Depression (CES-D) scores ≥ 50 , respectively (Leung et al., 2013; Miyake et al., 2016). Neither study reported significant relationships between supplementation and PPD at their respective follow-up periods, stipulating that Vitamin D produced no benefits (Leung et al., 2013; Miyake et al., 2016).

Of the prospective cohort studies that produced significant results, all five of them used maternal serum 25(OH)-D as their supplement of interest. Accortt et al. (2016), Gur et al. (2015), Lamb et al. (2018), and Robinson et al. (2014) measured 25(OH)-D at various points during the gestational period prior to childbirth, and compared these levels in women with and without PPD, diagnosed using the EPDS (Accortt, Schetter, Peters, & Cassidy-Bushrow, 2016; Gur et al., 2015; Lamb et al., 2018; Robinson et al., 2014). Gur et al. (2015) found a negative correlation between the two variables at 1 week, 6 weeks, and 6 months postpartum, with r values of -0.2, -0.2, and -0.3 ($p < 0.05$) respectively (Gur et al., 2015). Similarly, Lamb et al. (2018) found a negative relationship between serum levels taken 14 weeks into gestation ($r = -0.23, p < 0.05$) and 6 weeks postpartum ($r = -0.22, p < 0.05$), and EPDS scores at 10 weeks postpartum; however, there was no significant correlation between 25(OH)-D levels measured at 32 weeks into gestation and EPDS scores at 10 weeks postpartum (Lamb et al., 2018). Robinson et al. (2014) determined that low gestation 25(OH)-D levels were a significant risk factor for PPD immediately after childbirth, with an odds ratio of 2.1 ($p < 0.05$) (Robinson et al., 2014). In Fu et al.'s (2015) cohort, serum 25(OH)-D levels were taken 24-48 hours postpartum, as opposed to during gestation (Fu, Liu, Tu, Yang, & Cao, 2015). The authors reported that 25(OH)-D levels were higher in women without PPD, and thus were potentially protective against the depression (OR=0.74, $p < 0.05$) (Fu et al., 2015).

Two of the included studies had case-control designs, separating women with PPD from those who did not have it. In the Abedi et al. (2018) study, serum 25(OH)-D levels were compared to the presence or absence of depression, using a BDI score ≥ 17 (Abedi, Boyari, Fakhri, & Jahanfar, 2018). Women with PPD were found to have lower 25(OH)-D levels compared to women without PPD, with the study citing an OR=3.30 ($p < 0.05$) for those with lower 25(OH)-D (Abedi et al., 2018). However, the cut-off level for 25(OH)-D was not defined in the article. In the second article, N. O. Nielsen et al. (2013) also used maternal blood concentrations to study a potential relationship between Vitamins D2 and D3, and PPD. Unlike the previous study, authors found no significant relationship between either vitamin and PPD (N. O. Nielsen et al., 2013).

A cross-sectional study by Lin et al. (2019) investigated potential Vitamin D and retinol relationships with PPD. Using serum 25(OH)-D and retinol levels at 6-8 weeks postpartum, no significant relationship was found between vitamin levels and presence of PPD (Lin et al., 2019).

The two randomized controlled trials (RCT) produced contradicting results. Vaziri et al. (2016) exposed pregnant women to either 0 or 2000IU of Vitamin D3 daily from 26-28 weeks into gestation until childbirth (Vaziri et al., 2016). The resulting data suggested that Vitamin D3 supplementation was protective against PPD at 4 and 8 weeks postpartum (Vaziri et al., 2016). At each time point, the mean EPDS scores of the trial group were lower than the scores of the placebo group, with an average score difference of 2.88 ($p < 0.05$) (Vaziri et al., 2016). In comparison, Williams et al. (2016) exposed pregnant women to either ≥ 20 ng/mL of Vitamin D per day or < 20 ng/mL of Vitamin D daily (Williams et al., 2016). After 6-8 weeks postpartum, no significant association was present between the two groups, indicating that Vitamin D is ineffective against PPD (Williams et al., 2016).

The exploratory study by Murphy et al. (2010) used a convenience sample to determine the ability of maternal 25(OH)-D to predict PPD diagnosis based on EPDS scores. Results showed a significant relationship between low

25(OH)-D levels and high EPDS scores, indicating that Vitamin D is protective against the depression (Murphy, Mueller, Hulsey, Ebeling, & Wagner, 2010).

3.2.2 Vitamin B

Of the studies researching Vitamin B, results showed that supplementation with Vitamins B1, B3, B6 and B12 had no effect on PPD; however, data involving folate, also known as Vitamin B9, were mixed. B-vitamin supplements are often taken by mothers to reduce anemia in the mother during pregnancy, as well as promote healthy neurodevelopment in the newborn, including the prevention of neural tube defects (Dror & Allen, 2012). The mothers in each of the included studies had no known prior health issues, but it is not known whether they had also ingested other supplements, as the studies did not inquire about other supplementation.

The Blunden et al. (2012) study looked at the effects of Vitamins B6, B12 and folate on PPD. Self-reported maternal intake levels of these vitamins pre- and during gestation were compared to EPDS scores at 6 months and 1 year postpartum. Results showed no relation between vitamin intake at any timepoint during gestation and EPDS scores at any time postpartum (Blunden et al., 2012).

Another prospective study by Chong et al. (2014) researched Vitamin B12 and its potential association with PPD. Maternal plasma vitamin concentrations were taken 26-28 weeks into gestation and compared to EPDS scores at 3 months postpartum (Chong et al., 2014). No statistically significant relationship was found between plasma Vitamin B12 levels and EPDS scores in mothers, supporting the results from the Blunden et al. (2012) study (Chong et al., 2014).

The aforementioned Leung et al. (2013) study also investigated Vitamins B1, B3, B6, B12 and folate, in addition to Vitamin D. In this cohort, no statistically significant associations were present between any of the B-vitamins and EPDS scores at 12 weeks postpartum either (Leung et al., 2013).

A fourth article, authored by Lewis et al. (2012), used a British cohort of pregnant women to study the effects of folate. The women self-reported folate supplementation 32 weeks into gestation, and were followed-up at 8 weeks, 8 months, and 21 months postpartum (Lewis, Araya, Leary, Davey Smith, & Ness, 2012). Although no statistically significant relationship was found between folate intake and PPD, measured by EPDS scores, at 8 weeks or 8 months postpartum, results found a significant inverse correlation between supplementation and EPDS scores at 21 months postpartum (Lewis et al., 2012). Mothers who took the supplements had a smaller increase in EPDS scores compared to mothers who did not take the supplements (Lewis et al., 2012).

Yan et al. (2017) also investigated folate, using a self-reported questionnaire about supplementation during the pregnancy period to investigate a possible relationship with PPD, measured with the Self-Rating Depression Scale (SDS) at 6-12 weeks postpartum (Yan et al., 2017). The authors reported that folate was protective against PPD if taken for more than six months during the pregnancy period (OR=0.76, $p<0.05$) (Yan et al., 2017).

3.2.3 Multivitamins

In the multivitamin study, Dagher & Shenassa (2012) explored a possible correlation between multivitamin intake at various timepoints in pregnancy and PPD. Although supplementation during the second and third trimesters had no significant impact on EPDS scores, supplementation during the first trimester had a significant and inversed correlation with EPDS scores ($r = -1.37$, $p < 0.05$) (Dagher & Shenassa, 2012). This indicates that multivitamin supplementation during the first trimester was somewhat protective against PPD, although intake at other timepoints was ineffective.

3.2.4 Minerals

The studies investigating minerals found no relationship between minerals and PPD overall, although one study found selenium to potentially have a protective effect against PPD. The other studies had statistically insignificant results, indicating that zinc, magnesium, calcium, iron and iodine generally have no relationship with PPD symptoms (Table 2). Typically, calcium, iron and magnesium help promote healthy neural development and tissue construction in the baby, while also reducing the risk of pre-eclampsia in the mother (Khayat, Fanaei, & Ghanbarzahi, 2017). Likewise, iodine also has a role in fetal neural development, but has an additional role in regulating maternal thyroid hormone levels, while selenium regulates fetal growth and development (Khayat et al., 2017). The mothers in each of the included studies had no known prior health issues, but it is not known whether they had also ingested other supplements, as the studies did not inquire about other supplementation.

In one triple blind randomized-controlled trial, Fard et al. (2017) used pregnant mothers to determine whether zinc and/or magnesium had an effect on EPDS scores at 8 weeks postpartum. Mothers were randomly assigned to an intervention group of either one zinc sulfate tablet daily, one magnesium sulfate tablet daily, or a placebo daily for 8 weeks (Fard et al., 2017). However, neither intervention group had significant difference in EPDS scores when compared to the placebo group, with authors concluding that magnesium and zinc did not influence PPD risk (Fard et al., 2017).

Another study using a retrospective cohort model investigated the effects of iron, zinc and calcium on self-reported PPD diagnosis based on diet during gestation. Similar to the Fard et al. study, neither iron, zinc, nor calcium intake had a significant impact on PPD (Hogg-Kollars, Mortimore, & Snow, 2011). Mothers with self-diagnosed PPD ingested similar amounts of the aforementioned minerals compared to mothers without PPD (Hogg-Kollars et al., 2011).

In addition to studying Vitamin D, Miyake et al. (2016) explored the effects of calcium on PPD, using the same prospective cohort. Mothers self-reported dietary intake of calcium during the gestation period and were monitored for PPD at 3-4 months postpartum with the CES-D scale (Miyake et al., 2016). Again, the authors noted no statistically significant relationship between calcium intake in the pregnancy period and PPD, indicating that calcium does not have an effect on PPD (Miyake et al., 2016).

In the Leung et al. (2013) study, a cohort of 475 pregnant women was monitored for any relationship between dietary intake of iodine, magnesium, selenium and zinc, and PPD. EPDS scores were taken at 12 weeks postpartum, where scores ≥ 12 were indicative of PPD, and compared to self-reported maternal supplement intake during the prenatal period. There were no significant relationships between iodine, iron, magnesium or zinc intake and EPDS scores (Leung et al., 2013). However, the authors reported a significant inverse relationship between selenium and EPDS (Leung et al., 2013). The mean ingestion of selenium in mothers later diagnosed PPD was approximately 19mcg, while the mean ingestion of selenium in mothers not diagnosed with PPD was approximately 25mcg ($p < 0.05$), suggesting that selenium may be protective against PPD (Leung et al., 2013).

3.2.5 Fatty Acids

Fifteen articles researched the effects of long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids (LC-PUFA), particularly n-3 PUFA and n-6 PUFA, as well as docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) and eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) on PPD. DHA and EPA specific studies were included in this review as they are commonly used examples of n-3 PUFA. These fatty acids are often used during the pregnancy period to improve newborn neurodevelopment and to regulate inflammation (Greenberg, Bell, & van Ausdal, 2008). The mothers in each of the studies had no known prior health issues, but it is not known whether they had also ingested other supplements, as the studies did not inquire about other supplementation. Results from these articles were mixed, with seven articles claiming protective effects, while the other eight suggesting no significant effects (Table 3).

Hoge et al. (2019), Markhus et al. (2013) and Parker et al. (2015) used similar protocols to each other, measuring n-3 PUFA and n-6 PUFA levels in maternal erythrocytes at various points in the gestation period. Hoge et al.

(2019) measured the fatty acid profile at an unspecified time in early pregnancy, while Markhus et al. (2013) analyzed the profile at 28 weeks into gestation, and Parker et al. (2015) used fatty acid profiles taken 36 weeks into gestation (Hoge et al., 2019; Markhus et al., 2013; Parker et al., 2015). The studies produced similar results, identifying a potential significant and negative correlation between total n-3 PUFA, DHA and EPA levels, and PPD (Hoge et al., 2019; Markhus et al., 2013; Parker et al., 2015). Hoge et al. (2019) indicated that DHA (OR=0.55, $p<0.05$) and total n-3 PUFA levels (OR=0.58, $p<0.05$) were strongly protective against PPD (Hoge et al., 2019). Correlation coefficients of -0.39 ($p<0.05$) between total n-3 PUFA and PPD, and of -0.41 ($p<0.05$) between DHA and PPD were also calculated (Markhus et al., 2013).

A n-6 PUFA/n-3 PUFA ratio was also found to be positively correlated with PPD (OR=2.09, $p<0.05$), indicating that high ratios may be a risk factor for PPD diagnosis (Hoge et al., 2019). Additionally, Parker et al. (2015) concluded that increased n-6 PUFA levels were related to an increased risk of PPD; women with EPDS scores ≥ 10 had approximately 27.1% of their erythrocyte fatty acid profile consisting of n-6 PUFA, compared to 26.8% in women with EPDS scores <9 (Parker et al., 2015). Note that serum levels were used as an objective measure of fatty acid intake by mothers during the gestation period. However, it should also be noted that research has shown significant decreases in n-3 PUFA and n-6 PUFA during normal pregnancy that are not associated with PPD alone, suggesting a potential confounder (Kitamura et al., 2017).

Three prospective cohorts found statistically significant results using self-reported questionnaires. Hamazaki et al. (2019) administered a questionnaire at an unspecified time in the mid-late gestational period on a cohort of 84 181 pregnant Japanese women (Hamazaki et al., 2019). Intake of foods high in n-3 PUFA was found to lower the risk of PPD in mothers at 6 months and 1 year postpartum (OR=0.80 at both time points, $p<0.05$). Likewise, Leung et al. (2013) found that the mean intake of n-3 PUFA in mothers with PPD was substantially less than the mean intake in mothers without PPD (Leung et al., 2013). Whereas mothers with PPD had an average intake of 90mg of n-3 PUFA during gestation, mothers without PPD ingested an average of 180mg ($p<0.05$) (Leung et al., 2013). The third study, by da Rocha & Kac (2012), compared self-reported intake of n-3 PUFA and n-6 PUFA in the first trimester to EPDS scores at least 30 days after childbirth (da Rocha & Kac, 2012). No significant relations were found between total n-3 PUFA or total n-6 PUFA intake and PPD, but the authors did conclude that increased ratios of n-6 PUFA/n-3 PUFA in mothers can be predictive of PPD (da Rocha & Kac, 2012). In mothers with n-6 PUFA/n-3 PUFA ratios greater than 9:1, the prevalence ratio of PPD was 2.72 ($p<0.05$) (da Rocha & Kac, 2012). In the Lin et al. (2019) cross-sectional study, maternal fatty acid profiles were taken at 6-8 weeks postpartum and referenced to EPDS scores, where a score ≥ 10 indicated PPD (Lin et al., 2019). The authors discovered that increased total n-3 PUFA levels (OR=0.994, $p<0.05$) and n-3 PUFA/n-6 PUFA ratios (OR=0.764, $p<0.05$) may be protective against PPD (Lin et al., 2019). As well, mothers with higher total n-6 PUFA levels were at a greater risk of PPD (OR=1.005, $p<0.05$) (Lin et al., 2019). However, despite being statistically significant, the calculated odds ratios were close to 1, potentially rendering the effects negligible. Note that fatty acid profiles in erythrocytes were used as an objective measure of maternal fatty acid intake during pregnancy, assuming that diet did not drastically change within the first 6-8 weeks after childbirth. However, it should also be noted that research has shown significant decreases in n-3 PUFA and n-6 PUFA during normal pregnancy that are not associated with PPD, suggesting a potential confounder (Kitamura et al., 2017).

Four of the studies finding no effects used prospective cohorts, one used a retrospective cohort, two used double-blind RCTs, and one used a cross-sectional design. Chong et al. (2015) and Sallis et al. (2014) investigated maternal LC-PUFA profiles in blood samples during the gestation period, comparing them to EPDS scores measured at 3 months and 8 weeks postpartum, respectively (Chong et al., 2015; Sallis, Steer, Paternoster, Davey Smith, & Evans, 2014). Both articles concluded that neither LC-PUFA, DHA, nor EPA were associated with a significant risk for PPD (Chong et al., 2015; Sallis et al., 2014). Note that antenatal maternal serum fatty acid profiles were used as objective measures of maternal fatty acid supplementation during the gestational period. However, it should also be noted that research has shown significant decreases in n-3 PUFA and n-6 PUFA during normal pregnancy that are not associated with PPD, suggesting a potential confounder (Kitamura et al., 2017).

Hamazaki et al. (2018) and Kobayashi et al. (2017) also used prospective cohorts, but measured fatty acid supplementation using self-reported questionnaires administered prior to childbirth (Hamazaki et al., 2018; Kobayashi et al., 2017). Pregnant women reported intake of fatty acid supplements at any dosage during the

gestational period, and then completed the EPDS questionnaire postpartum. Self-reported intake of any fatty acid did not affect the risk of PPD in mothers, regardless of dosage (Hamazaki et al., 2018; Kobayashi et al., 2017).

One study conducted in Austria asked mothers to complete questionnaires about diet during gestation, with a particular interest in n-3 PUFA. In this retrospective cohort, maternal intake was analyzed against self-diagnosis of PPD (Hogg-Kollars et al., 2011). There was no significant difference in n-3 PUFA intake between mothers who diagnosed themselves with PPD and mothers without PPD, concluding that there was no association between the two variables (Hogg-Kollars et al., 2011).

Another study investigated self-reported daily n-3 PUFA intake in mothers, using a cross-sectional design. Comparing mothers with EPDS scores ≥ 10 with mothers with lower EPDS scores, Cosatto, Else, & Meyer (2010) found no significant correlation between daily n-3 PUFA intake during and post childbirth, and a PPD diagnosis (Cosatto, Else, & Meyer 2010).

One double blind RCT used pregnant women to identify potential protective effects of n-3 PUFA against PPD, measured by EPDS scores. Pregnant women were either exposed to three n-3 PUFA rich capsules per day, for a daily total of 800mg of DHA and 100mg of EPA, or one placebo daily (Makrides et al., 2010). Using follow-up EPDS tests at 6 weeks and 6 months postpartum, significant differences in the total percent of women with EPDS scores >12 between each intervention group at either timepoint were not reported (Makrides et al., 2010). Again, n-3 PUFA did not produce any protective effect against PPD.

Vaz et al. (2017) used a similar protocol, exposing pregnant women to either six 1.8g capsules of n-3 PUFA daily, for a daily total of 1.08g of EPA and 0.72g of DHA, or six placebo pills daily (Vaz, Farias, Adegboye, Nardi, & Kac, 2017). Comparing EPDS scores of the two intervention groups at 4-6 weeks postpartum, no significant differences were found (Vaz et al., 2017). Treatment did not affect the risk of PPD in pregnant women, as also found in the previous study (Vaz et al., 2017).

3.2.6 Antibiotics and Probiotics

There were a limited number of studies investigating the effects of antibiotics and probiotics on postpartum depression; however, the two included studies produced significant results suggesting that antibiotic usage is a risk factor for PPD while probiotic supplementation may be protective (Table 4).

In the one study evaluating antibiotics, Murphy et al. (2018) used a prospective cohort of 120 pregnant mothers, comparing self-reported intake of antibiotics with follow-up EPDS scores at 1 month, 2 months, 3 months and 6 months postpartum (Murphy, Paul, Dunlop, & Corwin, 2018). The included cohort of mothers had antibiotic exposure during the intrapartum or postpartum period, and had no other known health issue (Murphy et al., 2018). The reasons provided for antibiotic usage included group B streptococcus positivity, uterine infection, premature rupture of membranes, fever, uterine tract infection, and upper respiratory infection; furthermore, exposure could be single or multiple dosage, taken enterally or parenterally (Murphy et al., 2018). However, the study did not separate study participants based on the ingested classes of antibiotics. Likewise, it is not known whether the mothers had ingested any other supplement, as the study did not inquire about other supplementation. Results determined a significant relationship between antibiotic intake and EPDS scores in the short-term post-childbirth (at 1 month and 2 months postpartum), where increased intake was correlated with increased EPDS scores ($\beta=1.69$ at 1 month postpartum and $\beta=1.55$ at 2 months postpartum, $p<0.05$) (Murphy et al., 2018). No significant relationship between the two variables was determined in the long-term, with no statistically significant correlation at 3 months or 6 months postpartum (Murphy et al., 2018). Since the authors did not distinguish the specific types of antibiotics that were taken by in their cohort though, it is difficult to determine whether certain types of antibiotics produced greater effects compared to others.

Slykerman et al. (2017) used pregnant mothers to monitor EPDS scores at 6 months postpartum, following the administration of *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* HN001 probiotics (Slykerman et al., 2017). Mothers were separated into treatment groups exposed to 0 or 6×10^9 colony forming units (cfu) of HN001 per day starting from enrollment

at 14-16 weeks gestation and ending at 6 months postpartum (Slykerman et al., 2017). It is not known whether the mothers had ingested any other supplement, as the study did not inquire about other supplementation, though the cohort of mothers reportedly had no known health issues (Slykerman et al., 2017). Results from this study suggested that probiotic intake with HN001 may have a protective effect against PPD. Mothers from the treatment group reported lower EPDS scores at 6 months postpartum compared to the placebo group (Slykerman et al., 2017). Whereas the HN001 group had a mean EPDS score of 7.7 at 6 months postpartum, the placebo group had a mean EPDS score of 9.0 ($p<0.05$) (Slykerman et al., 2017).

3.2.7 Combination of Supplements

A limited number of studies investigated the combined effects of dietary supplements on PPD. However, based on the included studies, results were mixed (Table 6). Most recently, Amini et al. (2020) used a double blind RCT to determine whether a combination of Vitamin D3 and calcium carbonate had a protective effect against PPD. Pregnant women were exposed to either a combination of Vitamin D3 and calcium carbonate daily, or one Vitamin D3 supplement daily, or one calcium carbonate supplement daily (Amini et al., 2020). Based on EPDS scores at 8 weeks postpartum, there was a significant reduction in EPDS scores in the treatment groups who were exposed to a combination of supplements or solely Vitamin D3; however, there was no significant reduction in EPDS scores in the treatment group exposed to only calcium carbonate (Amini et al., 2020). Furthermore, there was a greater mean reduction in EPDS scores in the vitamin only group (mean reduction of 4.16, $p<0.05$) than in the combination supplement group (mean reduction of 1.70, $p<0.05$), suggesting that Vitamin D3 was more effective at reducing PPD symptoms when taken individually rather than when combined with calcium (Amini et al., 2020).

Another study, conducted by Nguyen et al. (2017), exposed pregnant women to a mixture of vitamins and minerals. Women were randomly provided with one of three interventions, each taken weekly: a multiple micronutrient supplement containing 15 different micronutrients plus 2 800 μ g of folate and 60mg of iron; a supplement containing only 2 800 μ g of folate and 60mg of iron; or, a supplement containing solely 2 800 μ g of folate (Nguyen et al., 2017). EPDS scores were compared at 3 months postpartum, with no significant differences among the first two interventions when compared to the folate group (Nguyen et al., 2017).

A third RCT by Paoletti et al. (2013) compared a commercially available multi-nutrient tablet with a tablet containing Vitamin D3 and calcium carbonate, each taken daily (Paoletti et al., 2013). The researchers used Elevit® (Bayer Pharmaceuticals, Leverkusen, Germany), a pregnancy multivitamin and mineral supplement, as the commercial tablet (Paoletti et al., 2013). At 15 and 30 days postpartum, the Elevit® group had significantly greater reductions in EPDS scores compared to the other intervention group (Paoletti et al., 2013).

The sole prospective cohort study investigating a combination of supplements studied whether a mixture of multivitamins and iodine was more effective at preventing PPD compared to solely multivitamins or a placebo. Wang et al. (2020) exposed pregnant women to either one multivitamin and 150 μ g of iodine per day, or one multivitamin with no iodine per day, or one placebo pill daily for at least three months during the gestational period (Wang et al., 2020). EPDS scores measured at one month after childbirth found that the intervention group exposed to a combination of multivitamins and iodine had significantly higher EPDS scores (mean EPDS score=5.0, $p<0.05$) compared to the other two intervention groups (mean EPDS score in multivitamin group=3.5, mean EPDS score in placebo group=3.0, $p<0.05$) (Wang et al., 2020). There were no significant differences between the multivitamin group and the placebo group (Wang et al., 2020). Although the authors did not specify which multivitamins were included in the supplements, this study contradicts other articles included in this scoping review, indicating that a combination of multivitamins and iodine may exacerbate the maternal risk of developing PPD.

4. Discussion

4.1 Main Findings

Many mothers with PPD cite a number of reasons for a lack of compliance with current treatments. Resultantly, dietary supplements are increasingly being looked at as an alternative remedy, focusing on prevention rather than treatment, for mothers who prefer naturopathic medicine over allopathic care. With the purpose of examining possible protective effects of various dietary supplements on PPD using current literature, the results from this review produced conflicting results.

The studies examining vitamin supplementation on PPD risk found mixed results. For example, as seen in Table 1, Abedi et al. (2018) found that women with lower serum 25(OH)-D were over three times more likely to have PPD than women with higher levels of 25(OH)-D (Abedi et al., 2018). However, Gould et al. (2015) concluded that 25(OH)-D levels have no correlation with PPD presence at 6 weeks or 6 months post-childbirth (Gould et al., 2015). Furthermore, another article about Vitamin D found that its potential to produce protective effects was specific to certain times during the gestational period (Lamb et al., 2018). Regarding folate intake, two studies found no significant protective effect against PPD (Blunden et al., 2012; Leung et al., 2013), but two other articles found that increased folate intake produced lower EPDS scores under certain conditions (i.e if supplementation was for >6 months during gestation, and if EPDS scores were measured at 21 month postpartum) (Lewis et al., 2012; Yan et al., 2017). Based on the included articles though, there was replicated evidence that other B-vitamins, not including folate, had no effect on PPD risk at any dosage or time point (Blunden et al., 2012; Chong et al., 2014; Leung et al., 2013). Additionally, the articles investigating retinol and multivitamins found that retinol had no protective effect against PPD, and that only multivitamin intake in the first trimester had a significant negative correlation with EPDS scores (Dagher & Shenassa, 2012; Lin et al., 2019). However, given that there was only one article available for each regarding retinol and multivitamin supplementation, these results cannot be considered conclusive. Thus, it is currently unclear whether Vitamin D, folate, retinol and multivitamins might prevent PPD from occurring in mothers. Vitamins B1, B3, B6 and B12, on the other hand, do not seem to have any effect on PPD.

The majority of studies examining mineral supplementation found no difference in PPD risk in mothers with higher or lower intake, regardless of the mineral type (Fard et al., 2017; Hogg-Kollars et al., 2011; Leung et al., 2013; Miyake et al., 2016). Including a variety of study designs (RCT, prospective and retrospective cohort), none of the studies suggested that iron, zinc, magnesium, calcium nor iodine had a statistically significant correlation with PPD after childbirth (Fard et al., 2017; Hogg-Kollars et al., 2011; Leung et al., 2013; Miyake et al., 2016). However, one study concluded that selenium intake in the prenatal period was protective against PPD, where mothers with PPD had, on average, a lesser intake of the mineral compared to mothers without depression (Leung et al., 2013). As this was only one article investigating selenium caution must be taken when using these findings in a clinical setting.

Literature regarding treatment with fatty acids found mixed results. The majority of articles found that supplementation with total n-3 PUFA, DHA or EPA had no significant effects on PPD (Chong et al., 2015; Cosatto et al., 2010; Hamazaki et al., 2018; Hogg-Kollars et al., 2011; Kobayashi et al., 2017; Makrides et al., 2010; Sallis et al., 2014; Vaz et al., 2017). These findings were consistent despite differing study designs, geographic locations, definitions of PPD, and lengths of follow up. However, six studies found a significant inverse relationship between these fatty acids and PPD (Leung et al., 2013; Lin et al., 2019; Hoge et al., 2019; Markhus et al., 2013, Parker et al., 2015; Hamazaki et al., 2019). The strength of this relationship, though, differed between studies. Whereas Hamazaki et al. (2019), Lin et al. (2019) and Markhus et al. (2013) found modest protective effects against PPD (Hamazaki et al., 2019; Lin et al., 2019; Markhus et al., 2013), Hoge et al. (2019) concluded that increased n-3 PUFA and DHA intake reduced the risk of PPD considerably (Hoge et al., 2019). Clearly, there is a lack of definitive understanding as to whether total n-3 PUFA, DHA and EPA intake can influence PPD risk. In regard to n-6 PUFA intake, increased supplementation may be a slight risk factor for PPD, although again, these effects may be minimal (Lin et al., 2019; Parker et al., 2015). The largest risk factor for PPD was an elevated n-6 PUFA/n-3

PUFA ratio (Hoge et al., 2019; da Rocha & Kac, 2012), but it is unclear how mothers could monitor this ratio via supplementation.

Although the included articles researching antibiotics and probiotics produced statistically significant findings, there were a limited number of studies. Only one article was available for each of these supplements, and thus, results were not replicated. Antibiotic usage during the gestational period produced higher EPDS scores and thus, were linked with increased risk of PPD in the first two months after childbirth (Murphy et al., 2018). This relationship was not found at 3 months and 6 months postpartum though, making it unclear how long-lasting the negative effects of antibiotics would be (Murphy et al., 2018). Given that the classes of antibiotics were not separated in this study, it is uncertain whether specific antibiotics produce more pronounced effects than others. One study reported that treatment with *L. rhamnosus* HN001 produced lower EPDS scores than in women not exposed to the probiotic (Slykerman et al., 2017). Nevertheless, other types of probiotics were not researched, and these results were not replicated. Thus, more research is needed into the effects of antibiotics and probiotics before definitive conclusions can be reached.

Regarding a combined exposure of various supplements, articles showed mixed results. Women taking commercially available Elevit® tablets, consisting of multi-nutrients, Vitamin D3 and calcium carbonate, had greater reductions in EPDS scores compared to women taking solely calcium and Vitamin D (Paoletti et al., 2013). However, these findings were not consistent in other studies, and were sometimes refuted. One study found that multivitamin and iodine supplementation produced EPDS scores higher than a placebo pill, with no significant changes between the placebo group and the group taking only multivitamins (Wang et al., 2020). Likewise, another study found that a multi-micronutrient supplement similar to Elevit® produced no differences in EPDS scores compared to folate supplementation (Nguyen et al., 2017), while a third concluded that a combination of Vitamin D3 and calcium was not as effective in reducing the risk of PPD as an individual Vitamin D3 capsule (Amini et al., 2020). Thus, it is unclear which way a combination of supplements influences PPD, if at all.

Results from this scoping review show a considerable lack of understanding regarding the effects of dietary supplements on PPD, with many studies showing mixed findings, and results regarding potential protective effects often not replicated. This dearth of evidence is noticeable in current Canadian and global guidelines, such as the 'Prenatal Nutrition Guidelines for Health Professionals' and the 'Family-Centred Maternity and Newborn Care: National Guidelines,' which were intended to provide the latest information on necessary maternal healthcare for Canadians (Canada & Health Canada, 2009; Public Health Agency of Canada, 2017). Neither of these documents provide recommendations on supplement usage for the prevention or treatment of PPD, only on its effects on other health problems (Canada & Health Canada, 2009; Public Health Agency of Canada, 2017). Likewise, in the World Health Organization's (WHO) 'WHO Recommendations on Antenatal Care for a Positive Pregnancy Experience,' there are no recommendations from the WHO regarding supplement usage for the prevention or treatment of PPD, only suggesting supplementation for other health problems (WHO, 2016). However, with the exception of n-6 PUFA and antibiotics, the included studies also did not conclude any negative impacts of supplements on PPD, meaning that although no effects may be witnessed in some women, supplement intake will often not exacerbate the risk of PPD. Resultantly, this scoping review could provide the foundation for new or updated policies regarding supplement intake, especially with selenium, HN001, folate, Vitamin D, and n-3 PUFA, to combat PPD.

4.2 Limitations

There were some limitations to this scoping review. This review was limited to two databases (Medline and PubMed) when searching for relevant articles. However, other databases may have additional articles regarding this topic. As well, this review used specific keywords and MeSH subheadings to identify relevant articles. The specific nature of the keywords and subheadings may have prevented the inclusion of other related studies.

Additionally, the studies for this review took place throughout the world and at different time points in the last 10 years. As such, different versions of PPD diagnostic tests were used in each of the studies, leading to an inconsistency in the definition of postpartum depression. For example, whereas some studies considered an EPDS score ≥ 10 to be classified as PPD, other studies considered an EPDS score ≥ 12 to be classified as PPD, and yet

other studies used different diagnostic checklists to diagnose PPD. The inclusion of these articles in this review, regardless of the administered diagnostic test, may lead to an underestimation or overestimation of the effects of certain dietary supplements on PPD, as there was no set definition of PPD applied in this scoping review given the relatively small number of studies evaluating each supplement.

Finally, many of the studies used serum levels or fatty acid profiles of erythrocytes to objectively measure maternal supplement intake. However, as previously mentioned, fatty acid profiles of erythrocytes have been determined to drastically change during pregnancy, even without the presence of PPD (Kitamura et al., 2017). Likewise, it is not known whether there are substantial changes to endogenous synthesis of fatty acids, including DHA and EPA, during the pregnancy period of a mother without PPD. Resultantly, these methods of data collection may provide some confounding bias, making the direction of the relationship between maternal fatty acid profiles/serum levels and PPD unclear.

4.3 Future Directions

This review highlights a lack of research regarding the effects of supplement co-exposure on PPD. Of the 39 included articles, only four studies analyzed the effects of multiple exposure simultaneously on PPD diagnosis. However, Health Canada recommends that multiple different supplements be taken before and during the gestational period, including Vitamin D, iron, and folic acid (Canada & Health Canada, 2009). As a result, mothers often consume numerous supplements during pregnancy, meaning that, further research is needed to better understand the combined effects of various supplement intake on PPD. Additionally, research is needed to take into account socioeconomic factors as well as effective dosage values, which may impact the efficacy of various supplement intake on PPD.

5. Conclusion

The results from this scoping review provide some understanding into the effects of various dietary supplements on PPD. Findings from the included studies support a relationship between certain supplements and PPD diagnosis, although most results are inconclusive or statistically insignificant. Future research is needed to better understand the combined effects of various supplements. This scoping review could be used to help guide new or updated policies regarding supplement intake to prevent PPD. Furthermore, this paper can lay the basis for future research to help attain greater insight into the effects of individual supplement intake and supplement co-exposure on postpartum depression.

6. Disclosure Statement

The authors have no potential conflict of interest to report.

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Figure 1. PRISMA diagram generated in Covidence, outlining the selection process for identifying relevant articles to include in the scoping review.

Table 1. Details of studies involving vitamin supplementation.

Study	Dietary Supplement of Interest	Study Design	Location	Participants	Intervention	Primary Outcomes	Definition of PPD	Length of Follow-Up
Abedi et al., 2018	25(OH)-D	Case-control study	Izeh, Iran	120 pregnant women (60 with PPD)	Serum 25(OH)-D levels post-birth	Women with PPD have less 25(OH)-D than women without PPD (OR=3.30)	BDI score $\geq$ 17	6-8 weeks postpartum
Accortt et al., 2016	25(OH)-D	Prospective cohort	Detroit, USA	91 African-American pregnant women	Serum 25(OH)-D levels pre-birth	Lower prenatal 25(OH)-D levels were associated with more PPD symptoms	EPDS scale used	4-6 weeks postpartum
Blunden et al., 2012	Folate, Vitamins B6 and B12	Prospective cohort	Southampton, England	2 856 pregnant women	Self-reported intake of vitamins pre- and during gestation	No association between vitamin intake pre- and during pregnancy, and EPDS scores	EPDS score $\geq$ 13	6 months-1 year postpartum
Chong et al., 2014	Vitamin B12	Prospective cohort	Singapore	709 pregnant women	Plasma Vitamin B12 concentrations taken between 26-28 weeks gestation	No association between plasma vitamin levels and PPD	EPDS score $\geq$ 13	3 months postpartum
Dagher & Shenassa, 2012	Unspecified multivitamin	Prospective cohort	Maryland, USA	526 pregnant women who took prenatal vitamins	Hospital interview at birth about vitamin intake	Only vitamin use in the first trimester had an inverse relationship with EPDS scores ($r=-1.37$) Vitamin intake at other trimesters were not associated with EPDS scores	EPDS scale used	8 weeks postpartum
Fu et al., 2015	25(OH)-D	Prospective cohort	Beijing, China	213 pregnant women	Serum 25(OH)-D levels at 24-48 hours postpartum	Serum 25(OH)-D levels were higher in those without PPD (OR=0.74)	EPDS score $\geq$ 12	3 months postpartum
Gould et al., 2015	25(OH)-D	Prospective cohort	Australia	1 040 pregnant women	Umbilical cord 25(OH)-D levels	No association between 25(OH)-D levels and PPD at 6 weeks or at 6 months	EPDS score $\geq$ 12	6 weeks and 6 months postpartum
Gur et al., 2015	25(OH)-D	Prospective cohort	Izmir, Turkey	179 pregnant women	Serum 25(OH)-D levels at second trimester	Significant negative correlation between 25(OH)-D and EPDS scores at 1 week, 6 weeks and 6 months postpartum ($r=-0.2$; $r=-0.2$; $r=-0.3$)	EPDS score $\geq$ 12	1 week, 6 weeks, and 6 months postpartum
Lamb et al., 2018	25(OH)-D	Prospective cohort	Southern California, USA	88 pregnant women	Maternal 25(OH)-D at 14 weeks and 32 weeks gestation, and 6 weeks postpartum	Significant inverse relationship between 25(OH)-D levels at 14 weeks gestation and 6 weeks postpartum, and EPDS scores ($r=-0.23$; $r=-0.22$)	EPDS score $\geq$ 10	10 weeks postpartum

						No significant relationship between 25(OH)-D levels at 32 weeks gestation and EPDS scores		
Leung et al., 2013	Vitamins B1, B3, B6, B9, B12, and D	Prospective cohort	Alberta, Canada	475 pregnant women	Self-reported prenatal supplement intake	No significant relationship between any vitamin intake and EPDS scores	EPDS score $\geq$ 10	12 weeks postpartum
Lewis et al., 2012	Folate	Prospective cohort	Bristol, England	6 809 pregnant women	Self-reported folate supplementation at 32 weeks gestation	No significant relationship between folate supplementation and PPD at 8 weeks or 8 months postpartum. Significant inverse relationship between folate supplementation and PPD at 21 months postpartum	EPDS scale used	8 weeks, 8 months, and 21 months postpartum
Lin et al., 2019	25(OH)-D and retinol	Cross-sectional study	Taipei, Taiwan	120 pregnant women (97 with PPD)	Serum 25(OH)-D and retinol levels at 6-8 weeks postpartum	No significant relationship between 25(OH)-D or retinol and PPD	EPDS score $\geq$ 10	N/A
Miyake et al., 2016	Vitamin D	Prospective cohort	Kyushu and Okinawa, Japan	1 319 mother-child pairs	Self-reported dietary intake of Vitamin D during pregnancy	No significant relationship between Vitamin D intake and PPD	CES-D score $\geq$ 16	3-4 months postpartum
P. K. Murphy et al., 2010	25(OH)-D	Exploratory descriptive study	Charleston, USA	97 postpartum women	Maternal 25(OH)-D levels measured monthly	Significant inverse relationship between 25(OH)-D levels and EPDS scores	EPDS score $\geq$ 9	Every month for first 7 months postpartum
N. O. Nielsen et al., 2013	Vitamins D2 and D3	Retrospective case-control study	Denmark	1 450 pregnant women (605 with PPD)	Maternal blood concentration of Vitamins D2 and D3	No significant relationship between either vitamin and PPD	Whoever filled prescriptions for antidepressants	N/A
Robinson et al., 2014	25(OH)-D	Prospective cohort	Perth, Australia	796 Caucasian pregnant women	Maternal blood concentration of 25(OH)-D at 18 weeks gestation	Significant inverse relationship between 25(OH)-D levels and PPD symptoms (OR=2.19)	EPDS score $\geq$ 6	3 days postpartum
Vaziri et al., 2016	Vitamin D3	Single-blind randomized controlled trial	Shiraz, Iran	153 pregnant women (79 in trial group, 75 in placebo group)	Either 2000IU of Vitamin D3/day from 26-28 weeks gestation to birth (trial group) or a placebo (placebo group)	Significant inverse relationship between vitamin intake and EPDS scores. (mean EPDS scores at 4 weeks: 4.59 in trial group, 7.36 in placebo group) (mean group)	EPDS score $>$ 13	4 and 8 weeks postpartum

						EPDS scores at 8 weeks: 4.19 in trial group, 7.18 in placebo group)		
Williams et al., 2016	Vitamin D	Double-blind randomized controlled trial	Michigan, USA	119 pregnant women (98 in high vitamin level group, 19 in low vitamin level group)	Either ≥ 20 ng/mL of Vitamin D per day (high vitamin group) or < 20 ng/mL of Vitamin D per day (low vitamin group)	No significant association between Vitamin D and BDI scores	BDI scale used	6-8 weeks postpartum
Yan et al., 2017	Folate	Prospective cohort	Tianjin, China	1 202 pregnant women	Self-reported questionnaire about folate supplementation	Significant inverse relationship between folate intake for > 6 months during pregnancy and PPD (OR=0.76)	SDS score ≥ 50	6-12 weeks postpartum

All numerical data are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The Accortt et al. (2016), Dagher & Shenassa (2012), Lewis et al. (2012), and Williams et al. (2016) studies used the EPDS scores as an independent variable, and thus did not define what they considered as PPD.

Table 2. Details of studies involving mineral supplementation.

Study	Dietary Supplement of Interest	Study Design	Location	Participants	Intervention	Primary Outcomes	Definition of PPD	Length of Follow-Up
Fard et al., 2017	Zinc sulfate and magnesium sulfate	Triple blind randomized-controlled trial	Tabriz, Iran	99 pregnant women (33 in each intervention group)	Either one 27mg zinc sulfate tablet daily, or one 320mg magnesium sulfate tablet daily, or one placebo daily for 8 weeks	No significant difference between any of the groups	EPDS score $\geq$ 13	8 weeks postpartum
Hogg-Kollars et al., 2011	Iron, zinc, and calcium	Retrospective cohort	Austria	400 mothers (83 had self-reported PPD)	Self-reported questionnaire about dietary foods during pregnancy	No significant difference of iron, zinc or calcium intake between mothers with PPD and mothers without PPD	Self-diagnosis of PPD	Unspecified
Leung et al., 2013	Iodine, iron, magnesium, selenium and zinc	Prospective cohort	Alberta, Canada	475 pregnant women	Self-reported prenatal supplement intake	No significant relationship between iodine, iron, magnesium or zinc intake and EPDS scores Significant inverse relationship between selenium intake and EPDS scores (mean intake of mothers with PPD=19mcg; mean intake of mothers without PPD=25mcg)	EPDS score $\geq$ 10	12 weeks postpartum
Miyake et al., 2016	Calcium	Prospective cohort	Kyushu and Okinawa, Japan	1 319 mother-child pairs	Self-reported intake of calcium during pregnancy	No significant relationship between calcium and PPD	CES-D score $\geq$ 16	3-4 months postpartum

All numerical data are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Table 3. Details of studies involving fatty acid supplementation.

Study	Dietary Supplement of Interest	Study Design	Location	Participants	Intervention	Primary Outcomes	Definition of PPD	Length of Follow-Up
Chong et al., 2015	LC-PUFA	Prospective cohort	Singapore	968 pregnant women	Plasma LC-PUFA measured at 26-28 weeks gestation	No significant association between PUFA levels and PPD	EPDS score $\geq$ 13	3 months postpartum
Cosatto et al., 2010	n-3 PUFA	Cross-sectional study	Australia	94 mothers (76 with PPD)	Self-reported questionnaire about daily fatty acid intake	No significant association with daily n-3 PUFA intake and PPD	EPDS score $\geq$ 10	N/A
Hamazaki et al., 2018	n-3 PUFA	Prospective cohort	Japan	77 661 pregnant women	Self-reported questionnaire about n-3 PUFA intake	No significant association between n-3 PUFA intake and PPD	EPDS score $\geq$ 9	1 month postpartum
Hamazaki et al., 2019	n-3 PUFA	Prospective cohort	Japan	84 181 pregnant women	Self-reported questionnaire about n-3 PUFA intake at middle to late pregnancy	Significant inverse relationship between n-3 PUFA intake and PPD at 6 months and 1 year postpartum (OR=0.80; OR=0.80)	EPDS score $\geq$ 9	6 months and 1 year postpartum
Hoge et al., 2019	n-3 PUFA and n-6 PUFA	Prospective cohort	Liege, Belgium	72 pregnant women	Maternal fatty acid profile in erythrocytes in early pregnancy	Significant inverse relationship between DHA and total n-3 PUFA, and PPD (OR=0.55; OR=0.58) Significant positive relationship between n-6 PUFA/n-3 PUFA ratio and PPD (OR=2.09)	Bromley PDS used	1 year postpartum

Hogg-Kollars et al., 2011	n-3 PUFA	Retrospective cohort	Austria	400 mothers (83 had self-reported PPD)	Self-reported questionnaire about dietary foods during pregnancy	No significant difference of n-3 fatty acid intake between mothers with PPD and mothers without PPD	Self-diagnosis of PPD	Unspecified
Kobayashi et al., 2017	DHA and EPA	Prospective cohort	Tokyo, Japan	967 pregnant women	Self-reported questionnaire about DHA and EPA intake at 26-40 weeks gestation	No significant association between DHA or EPA intake and PPD at either timepoint	EPDS score ≥ 9	1 month and 6 months postpartum
Leung et al., 2013	Omega-3 fatty acids	Prospective cohort	Alberta, Canada	475 pregnant women	Self-reported prenatal supplement intake	Significant inverse relationship between omega-3 fatty acid intake and PPD (mean intake of mothers with PPD=90mg; mean intake of mothers without PPD=180mg)	EPDS score ≥ 10	12 weeks postpartum
Lin et al., 2019	n-3 PUFA and n-6 PUFA	Cross-sectional study	Taipei, Taiwan	120 pregnant women (97 with PPD)	Maternal fatty acid profile in erythrocytes at 6-8 weeks postpartum	Significant slight inverse relationship between total n-3 PUFA and n-3 PUFA/n-6 PUFA ratio, and PPD (OR=0.994; OR=0.764) Significant slight positive relationship between total n-6 PUFA and PPD (OR=1.005)	EPDS score ≥ 10	N/A
Makrides et al., 2010	DHA and EPA	Double blind randomized-controlled trial	Melbourne, Australia	2 399 pregnant women (1 197 in the trial group, 1 202 in	Either three 500mg of n-3 PUFA-rich capsules per day (total of 800mg of DHA and 100mg of	No significant difference between the percent of women with PPD at either timepoint	EPDS score > 12	6 weeks and 6 months postpartum

				the placebo group)	EPA) (trial group) or one 500mg of vegetable oil capsule per day (placebo group)	between the trial and placebo groups		
Markhus et al., 2013	DHA and EPA	Prospective cohort	Western Norway	35 pregnant women	Maternal fatty acid profile in erythrocytes at 28 weeks gestation	Significant inverse relationship between total n-3 PUFA, DHA and n-3 PUFA/n-6 PUFA ratio, and PPD ($r=-0.39$; $r=-0.41$; $r=-0.31$)	EPDS score ≥ 10	3 months postpartum
Parker et al., 2015	n-3 PUFA and n-6 PUFA	Prospective cohort	Australia	773 pregnant women between 34 and 37 weeks gestation	Maternal fatty acid profile in erythrocytes at 36 weeks gestation	Significant inverse relationship between EPA levels and n-3PUFA, and PPD (mean percent of EPA in erythrocyte: 0.5% in women with PPD, 0.6% in women without PPD) (mean percent of n-3 PUFA in erythrocyte: 9.1% in women with PPD, 9.3% in women without PPD) Significant positive relationship between n-6 PUFA levels and PPD (mean percent of n-6 PUFA in erythrocyte: 27.1% in women with PPD, 26.8% in women without PPD)	EPDS score ≥ 10	3 months postpartum

da Rocha & Kac, 2012	Omega-3 and omega-6 fatty acids	Prospective cohort	Rio de Janeiro, Brazil	106 pregnant women	Self-reported questionnaire about dietary intake in the first trimester	Greater prevalence ratio of PPD in women with an omega-6/omega-3 ratio > 9:1 (PR=2.72)	EPDS score $\geq$ 11	At least 30 days postpartum
Sallis et al., 2014	DHA and EPA	Prospective cohort	Southwest England	2 757 mothers	Maternal antenatal fatty acid profile in blood samples	No significant association between EPA or DHA and PPD	EPDS score > 12	8 weeks postpartum
Vaz et al., 2017	DHA and EPA	Double blind randomized-controlled trial	Rio de Janeiro, Brazil	32 pregnant women (15 in trial group, 17 in placebo group)	Either six 1.8g of n-3 PUFA-rich capsules per day (total of 1.08g of EPA and 0.72g of DHA) (trial group) or six capsules of soybean oil per day (placebo group). Capsule intake lasted 16 weeks starting at 22-24 weeks gestation	No significant difference between EPDS scores of trial group and placebo group	EPDS score $\geq$ 11	4-6 weeks postpartum

All numerical data are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Table 4. Details of studies pertaining to antibiotic and probiotic supplementation.

Study	Dietary Supplement of Interest	Study Design	Location	Participants	Intervention	Primary Outcomes	Definition of PPD	Length of Follow-Up
J. R. Murphy et al., 2018	Unspecified antibiotics	Prospective cohort	N/A	120 pregnant women	Self-reported antibiotic exposure between intrapartum through the first 14 days postpartum	Significant positive relationship between antibiotic intake and EPDS scores at 1 month and 2 months postpartum ($\beta=1.69$; $\beta=1.55$) No significant relationship between antibiotic intake and EPDS scores at 3 months and 6 months postpartum	EPDS scale used	1 month, 2 months, 3 months, and 6 months postpartum
Slykerman et al., 2017	<i>Lactobacillus rhamnosus</i> HN001 probiotic	Double blind randomized-controlled trial	Auckland and Wellington, New Zealand	380 pregnant women (193 in the trial group, 187 in the placebo group)	Either 6×10^9 cfu of HN001 per day (trial group) or one placebo capsule per day (placebo group) from enrollment into study to 6 months postpartum	The trial group reported significantly lower EPDS scores compared to the placebo group at 6 months postpartum (mean EPDS scores: 7.7 in trial group, 9.0 in placebo group)	EPDS score > 12	6 months postpartum

All numerical data are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The J. R. Murphy et al. (2018) study used the EPDS scores as an independent variable, and thus did not define what they considered to be PPD

Table 5. Details of studies involving a combination of dietary supplements.

Study	Dietary Supplement of Interest	Study Design	Location	Participants	Intervention	Primary Outcomes	Definition of PPD	Length of Follow-Up
Amini et al., 2020	Vitamin D3 and calcium	Double blind randomized-controlled trial	N/A	81 pregnant women at risk of PPD (had EPDS scores > 12 during gestation) (27 in each intervention group)	Either one Vitamin D3+calcium carbonate supplement per day, or one Vitamin D3+placebo supplement per day, or one placebo+calcium carbonate supplement per day	Significant reductions in EPDS scores were evident in the vitamin+calcium group (mean EPDS score reduction=1.7) and the vitamin+placebo group (mean EPDS score reduction=4.16) No significant reductions in EPDS scores were evident in the placebo+calcium carbonate group	EPDS score > 12	8 weeks postpartum
Nguyen et al., 2017	Multiple micronutrients, folate, and iron	Double blind-randomized controlled trial	Northern rural Vietnam	1 465 pregnant women at risk PPD (472 in MM group, 478 in IFA group, 515 in FA group)	Either multiple micronutrients (15 micronutrients including 2800µg folate + 60mg iron) (MM group), iron and folate (2800µg folate + 60mg iron) (IFA group), or folate (2800µg folate) (FA group) per week	No significant difference in EPDS scores when comparing MM or IFA groups with FA group	EPDS score ≥ 4	3 months postpartum
Paoletti et al., 2013	Multi-nutrients, calcium, and vitamin D3	Double-blind randomized controlled trial	Cagliari, Italy	552 pregnant women (274 in the multi-nutrient group, 278 in the calcium+vitamin D group)	Either 1 Elevit® tablet (contains several different vitamins and minerals) daily (multi-nutrient group), or 1 calcium+vitamin D	Significant reductions in EPDS scores from baseline were more evident in the multi-nutrient group than the other group at both	EPDS score ≥ 12	15 days and 30 days postpartum

					tablet (500mg of calcium and 400IU of Vitamin D3) taken daily (calcium+vitamin D group)	timepoints (mean EPDS score difference at 15 days and 30 days=-2.2 and -3.1 for multi-nutrient group compared to -1.2 and -1.6 for the other group)		
Wang et al., 2020	Multivitamins and iodine	Prospective cohort	Shenyang, China	648 pregnant women (234 in group A, 220 in group B, 195 in group C)	Either one multivitamin+150µg of iodine daily (group A) or one multivitamin with no iodine daily (group B) or placebo daily (group C) for 3+ months during pregnancy	EPDS scores of group A were significantly higher than groups B and C (mean EPDS score=5 in group A, compared to 3.5 in group B and 3 in group C) No significant difference between groups B and C	EPDS score ≥ 10	1 month postpartum

All numerical data are statistically significant ($p<0.05$).

Appendix**Table A.** Keywords used for Medline search. Keywords and subject headings for the dietary supplements were combined with keywords and subject headings for postpartum depression via “AND”.

Keywords and Subject Headings (MeSH)	
Dietary supplement search	(probiotic.mp. OR Probiotics/) OR (Iron/ OR Vitamins/ OR Dietary Supplements/ OR Vitamin D/ OR multivitamin.mp.) OR (herbal supplement.mp.) OR (Drugs, Chinese Herbal/ OR Plant Extracts/ OR Plant Preparations/ OR Plants, Medicinal/ OR herbal drug.mp. OR herbal product.mp.) OR (antibiotic.mp. OR Anti-Bacterial Agents/) OR (Fatty Acids, Omega-3/ OR Fatty Acids, Nonesterified/ OR Fatty Acids/ OR Dietary Fats/ OR Fatty Acids, Unsaturated/ OR Fish Oils/ OR Fatty Acids, Omega-6/ OR Docosahexaenoic Acids/ OR Eicosapentaenoic Acid/ OR fatty acid*.mp. OR omega 6 fatty acid*.mp. OR omega 3 fatty acid*.mp. OR dha.mp. OR epa.mp.) OR (Vitamin E/ OR Vitamin A/ OR Vitamin D/ OR Ascorbic Acid/ OR vitamin a*.mp.)
Postpartum depression search	postpartum depression.mp OR Depression, Postpartum/

Table B. Keywords used for PubMed search. Keywords and subject headings for the dietary supplements were combined with keywords and subject headings for postpartum depression via “AND”.

Keywords and Subject Headings (MeSH)	
Dietary supplement search	(probiotic*) OR (((multivitamin*) OR (vitamin*)) OR (dietary supplement)) OR ((((((herbal supplement) OR (herbal product)) OR (herbal drug)) OR (chinese herbal drug)) OR (plant extract*)) OR (plant preparation*)) OR (medicinal plant*)) OR ((antibiotic*) OR (anti-bacterial agent*)) OR (((((((fatty acid) OR (omega-3 fatty acid)) OR (omega-6 fatty acid)) OR (dietary fat*)) OR (fish oil*)) OR (unsaturated fatty acid)) OR (nonesterified fatty acid)) OR (docosahexaenoic acid)) OR (eicosapentaenoic acid))
Postpartum depression search	postpartum depression*

Table C. Summary of the quality assessments for the cohort studies included in this review, using the CASP Checklist.

Study (Author & Year)	Overall Quality
Accort et al., 2016	Good
Blunden et al., 2012	Good
Chong et al., 2014	Good
Chong et al., 2015	Good
Dagher & Shenassa, 2012	Satisfactory
Fu et al., 2015	Satisfactory
Gould et al., 2015	Satisfactory
Gur et al., 2015	Satisfactory
Hamazaki et al., 2018	Satisfactory
Hamazaki et al., 2019	Good
Hogg-Kollars et al., 2011	Poor
Hoge et al., 2019	Satisfactory
Kobayashi et al., 2017	Good
Lamb et al., 2018	Satisfactory
Leung et al., 2013	Good
Lewis et al., 2012	Good
Markhus et al., 2013	Good
J. R. Murphy et al., 2018	Satisfactory
Miyake et al., 2016	Satisfactory
Parker et al., 2015	Satisfactory
Robinson et al., 2014	Poor
da Rocha & Kac, 2012	Good
Sallis et al., 2014	Good
Wang et al., 2020	Good
Yan et al., 2017	Satisfactory

Table D. Summary of the quality assessments for the case-control and cross-sectional studies included in this review.

Study (Author & Year)	Study Design	Quality Assessment Tool	Overall Quality
Abedi et al., 2018	Case-control	Downs and Black Checklist	22/32
Cosatto et al., 2010	Cross-sectional	Downs and Black Checklist	22/32
Lin et al., 2019	Cross-sectional	Downs and Black Checklist	25/32
N. O. Nielsen et al., 2013	Case-control	Downs and Black Checklist	25/32

Table E. Summary of the quality assessments for the randomized-controlled trials included in this review, using the Cochrane Risk of Bias tool.

Study (Author & Year)	Domain	Risk of Bias
Amini et al., 2020	Selection bias	Low

	Reporting bias	Low
	Performance bias	Low
	Attrition bias	Unclear
	Selection bias	Low
Fard et al., 2017	Reporting bias	Low
	Performance bias	Low
	Attrition bias	Low
	Selection bias	Low
Makrides et al., 2010	Reporting bias	Low
	Performance bias	Low
	Attrition bias	Low
	Selection bias	Low
Nguyen et al., 2017	Reporting bias	Low
	Performance bias	Low
	Attrition bias	Low
	Selection bias	Low
Paoletti et al., 2013	Reporting bias	High
	Performance bias	Unclear
	Attrition bias	Unclear
	Selection bias	Low
Slykerman et al., 2017	Reporting bias	Unclear
	Performance bias	Low
	Attrition bias	Low
	Selection bias	Unclear
Vaz et al., 2017	Reporting bias	Low
	Performance bias	Low
	Attrition bias	Unclear
	Selection bias	Low
Vaziri et al., 2016	Reporting bias	Unclear
	Performance bias	High
	Attrition bias	Low
	Selection bias	Low
Williams et al., 2016	Reporting bias	High
	Performance bias	Low
	Attrition bias	Low